

Prospective Observational Study of Emergency Peripartum Hysterectomy in Modern Obstetrics

Vandana Kumari¹, Nitish Kumar Ranjan²

¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Assistant Director, Department of Cardiology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Cardiology, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 05-03-2022 / Revised: 20-03-2022 / Accepted: 06-04-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Nitish Kumar Ranjan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: To study about emergency peripartum hysterectomy in modern obstetrics in a tertiary care hospital in Bihar

Methods: This prospective observational study was carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for a duration of 5 months from October 2021 to February 2022. Age, parity, traumatic or atonic PPH, risk factors, complications were all studied in detail and analysed.

Results: 40 women underwent peripartum hysterectomy, accounting to an incidence of 0.10%. Incidence of subtotal hysterectomy after caesarean delivery was higher as compared to vaginal deliveries. The common indications were uterine atony (47.5%), uterine rupture of scarred and unscarred uterus (40%), placenta previa of major degree (22.5%). Post-operatively patients developed DIC (37.5%), 6 patients developed febrile illness (15%), 4 patients of ruptured uterus experienced injury to the bladder (10%). Maternal mortality in this study was 12.5%.

Conclusions: Hysterectomy is a lifesaving procedure to control postpartum hemorrhage but is associated with significant maternal morbidity and mortality. Uterine atony, uterine ruptures, also due to prior caesarean delivery, placenta previa were identified as risk factors.

Keywords: Hysterectomy, Risk Factors, Maternal Mortality.

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Peripartum hysterectomy, a hysterectomy performed at the time of delivery or in the immediate postpartum period, is one of the most severe complications in obstetrics and is related to significant maternal mortality and morbidity[1-4]. Typically reserved for situations in which severe obstetric hemorrhage fails to respond to conservative treatment, peripartum hysterectomy is associated with severe blood loss, risk of

transfusion, intraoperative complications, and significant postoperative morbidity. It is important to estimate national incidence rates and trends for peripartum hysterectomy to improve obstetric practice and to assess risks and complications of pregnancy. Hospital-based retrospective case-reviews in the United States report incidence rates for peripartum hysterectomy ranging from 0.6 to 2.28 per

1,000 births^{1-3,5-8}. However, these studies are unable to provide reliable national incidence estimates because they were conducted in single institutions with small samples. Furthermore, their findings may be influenced by patient characteristics or practitioner practice patterns for hysterectomy at individual institutions. Several studies examined pregnancy-related factors associated with risk for peripartum hysterectomy. Generally, these studies report a greater than 10-fold higher incidence of peripartum hysterectomy among women who have previously delivered by cesarean section than among those who have not^[2,6-9]. This finding deserves closer examination, given the increasing rate of cesarean deliveries in the United States, even among low-risk women^[10]. However, few studies examined the effect of previous cesarean deliveries within the context of the current mode of delivery. Another reported risk factor for peripartum hysterectomy is multiple births,⁵ the rate of which is also increasing in the United States^[11]. It is important to note, however, that other studies were small and limited in the ability to examine risk factors for the procedure while adequately controlling for potential confounding factors. Uterine atony, most commonly found in prolonged, augmented and/or obstructed labour, such uteruses respond poorly to oxytocic. The majority of these cases occur at the time of caesarean section for dystocia or cephalopelvic disproportion. In case of rupture within prior caesarean section scar, if haemorrhage cannot be controlled hysterectomy is necessary^[12]. Traumatic rupture following instrumental delivery, obstructed labour, inversion of uterus, induced labour is also possible. Secondary post-partum haemorrhage secondary to retained products and sepsis may rarely require hysterectomy

Material and methods

This prospective observational study was carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for a duration of 5 months extending from October 2021 to February 2022. After taking informed consent detailed history was taken from the patient or the relatives if the patient was not in good condition. Total 40 patients who underwent peripartum hysterectomy were included into the study.

Inclusion criteria

- Patients who suffered severe post-partum haemorrhage and did not respond to conservative management, leading to emergency peripartum hysterectomy.
- Patients with ruptured uterus of both scared and unscared uterus which could not be repaired, leading to emergency peripartum hysterectomy.

Exclusion criteria

- Hysterectomies performed for gynaecological cause were excluded from the study.

Data abstracted included demographic data – age, parity, mode of delivery, prior caesarean sections, presence of placenta previa, presence of uterine rupture & uterine atony as a cause of PPH and traumatic PPH. The postsurgical complications, duration of hospital stay, maternal mortality & morbidity were recorded. Descriptive analyses were carried out to summarize relevant variables.

Results

40 patients underwent emergency peripartum hysterectomy, yielding to an incidence of 0.10%. 12 (30%) patients underwent emergency peripartum hysterectomy following vaginal delivery, among whom 2 (5.0%) patients had instrumental delivery and 26 (65%)

following caesarean section. Age distribution among the patients who underwent hysterectomy revealed that 2 patient was <20years of age (5.0%), 32 (80%) were between the age group of 21-30 and 6 (15%) were of age group 31-40. Parity distribution showed that 6 were primipara (15%), parity of 2 were 18 (45%) and parity of 3 were 13 (32.5%) and beyond parity 3 were 3 (7.5%). Table 1.

Table 2 shows the age-parity distribution and mode of delivery. 26 patients in the

study underwent caesarean sections, among them 10 patients were prior 1 LSCS (25%), 2 patients were prior 2 LSCS (5%). 9 (22.5%) patients had placenta previa, 1 (2.5%) patient presented with a combination of rupture uterus and placenta previa, underwent caesarean section, 1 (2.5%) patient presented with placenta previa and abruption placenta. The incidence of hysterectomy did not increase significantly in women with parity of 3 and beyond.

Table 1: Demographic of patients

Emergency hysterectomy		
Age	N=40	%
<20	02	5.0%
21-30	32	80%
31-40	6	15%
Parity		
1	6	15%
2	18	45%
3	13	32.5%
>3	3	7.5%
Mode of delivery		
Vaginal	12	30%
Caesarean	26	65%
Instrumental	2	5.0%

The most common indications out of the incidence were atonic PPH, noted in 19 patients (47.5%), following vaginal delivery were 7 (17.5%), following caesarean section were 12 (30%). Indication for rupture uterus

were 19 (47.5%), 8 (20%) following rupture of an unscarred uterus and 8 (20%) following rupture of scarred uterus. Due to secondary post- partum haemorrhage were 4 (10%). Acute inversion of uterus was 1(2.5%). table 3.

Table 2: Risk factors of emergency hysterectomy

Emergency hysterectomy		
Risk factor		
Caesarean section	26	%
Prior no LSCS	14	35%
Prior 1 LSCS	10	25%
Prior 2 LSCS	2	5%
Prior 3 LSCS	0	
Placenta previa		

Yes	9	22.5%
No	31	77.5%
Parity		
3	13	30.2%
>3	4	9.3%

Table 3: Indications for emergency peripartum hysterectomy

Emergency hysterectomy		
Indications		
Atonic uterus	19	47.5%
Rupture of scarred uterus	8	20%
Rupture of unscarred uterus (spontaneous rupture)		
a) primigravida	8	20%
b) multigravida	1 7	
Secondary PPH	4	10%
Acute inversion of uterus	1	2.5%

Table 4 shows that Out of 40 patients, 12 (30%) patients experienced intra-operative hypotension, (15%) developed febrile illness, 26 (65%) required ICU care. The mean hospital stays of the patients <10days were 14 (25.5%), >10days were 21 (52.5%) patients. This table shows the associated maternal morbidity with peripartum hysterectomy. Although peripartum hysterectomy is a lifesaving procedure, it is associated with significant morbidity. Table 5 illustrates the complications patients' experienced following hysterectomy. None of the 40 patients

required re-laparotomy, 15 (37.5%) patients went into DIC, 4 (10%) experienced bladder injury due to involvement of bladder along the rupture of uterus, repair done simultaneously during hysterectomy, 2 (5%) patients developed vesicovaginal fistula postoperatively. 5 (12.5%) patients who underwent emergency peripartum hysterectomy died during post-operative period. Maternal mortality was 12.5% in the study. 6 (15%) patients underwent an associated procedure for control of haemorrhage -bilateral internal iliac artery ligation.

Table 4: Observations of patients

Observations		%
Intraoperative hypotension	12	30%
Febrile illness	6	15%
ICU admission	26	65%
Mean hospital stay		
<10days	14	35%
>10days	21	52.5%

Table 5: Complications noted in the study

Complications	Emergency hysterectomy
DIC	15 (37.5%)
Injury to the bladder	4 (10%)
Death	5 (12.5%)
Vesicovaginal fistula	2 (5%)

1 patient was second gravida with central placenta previa, underwent caesarean section for the same, also underwent subtotal hysterectomy due to uncontrollable bleeding from the placental bed, patient expired intra-operative due to irreversible shock. 1 patient delivered by operative vaginal delivery, developed atonic PPH, which did not respond to conservative management, underwent hysterectomy, died on the same post-operative day due to irreversible shock following massive blood loss. 3 patients expired post-operatively as a consequence of DIC

Discussion

PPH along with sepsis and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy is a major cause of maternal mortality in India. Peripartum hysterectomy is a lifesaving surgery performed on a mother with intractable obstetric hemorrhage. In active management of third stage of labor, drugs such as misoprostol and oxytocin among other measures have markedly reduced maternal deaths from PPH. However, describing a reduction in maternal mortality rate is just describing the tip of an iceberg. The WHO has thus emphasized on the concept of maternal near miss [13]. Any pregnant woman who undergoes peripartum hysterectomy thus could have potentially died without timely and proper management.

The incidence of peripartum hysterectomy is increasing in this era not because of improperly managed third stage of labor or obstructed labor but most likely because of increasing incidence of cesarean sections. Chances of repeat cesarean sections thus increase. Emergency peripartum

hysterectomy is a lifesaving procedure of choice in cases of intractable hemorrhage and catastrophic rupture of uterus[14]. It is an unequivocal marker of severe acute maternal morbidity. It is associated with high index of maternal mortality and morbidity.

In developed countries, the reported incidence of emergency hysterectomy is below 0.1% of the total normal deliveries performed, while in developing countries, the incidence rates are as high as 1-5/ 1000 of all the deliveries performed. The incidence in the present study is 1.4 per 1000 deliveries. The primary reason for this higher incidence is due to the fact that our hospital is a referral center to most of the primary health care centers in surrounding rural areas. Majority of the patients are unbooked and deliver outside the health facilities unsupervised or poorly supervised and are referred in a deteriorated state.

The main indications for peripartum hysterectomy in developed countries are uterine atony and abnormal placentation, where as in developing countries, it was rupture of uterus and atony of uterus[15]. The most common causes of EPH in our study are atonic uterus, rupture uterus of unscarred and scarred uterus. Uterine rupture remains one of the serious obstetric complications even in modern obstetrics[16]. Lack of health information, illiteracy, poor antenatal care, poverty, home delivery by birth attendants, delay in referrals all contribute to uterine rupture. Injudicious use of oxytocin and trial of labour was the common cause, whereas prolonged obstructed labour was the second common cause.

In our analysis, the incidence of peripartum hysterectomy is 1/1000 deliveries, which is near to incidence of 0.2 and 5.4 in 1000 deliveries [17,18]. In our study, the most common indications of peripartum hysterectomy were atonic uterus (47.5%), and rupture uterus (40%). Similar study have been done by Saxena et al [19].

Conclusions

Hysterectomy is a lifesaving procedure to control postpartum hemorrhage but is associated with significant maternal morbidity and mortality. Uterine atony, uterine rupture, also due to prior caesarean delivery, placenta previa were identified as risk factors. The incidence in this part of Bihar was found to be significantly high as compared to other area of Bihar.

Reference

- Kastner ES, Figueroa R, Garry D, Maulik D. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy: experience at a community teaching hospital. *Obstet Gynecol* 2002; 99:971–5.
- Bakshi S, Meyer BA. Indications for and outcomes of emergency peripartum hysterectomy: a five-year review. *J Reprod Med* 2000; 45:733–7.
- Zelop CM, Harlow BL, Frigoletto FD Jr, Safon LE, Saltzman DH. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1993; 168:1443–8.
- Castaneda S, Karrison T, Cibils LA. Peripartum hysterectomy. *J Perinat Med* 2000; 28:472–81.
- Francois K, Ortiz J, Harris C, Foley MR, Elliott JP. Is peripartum hysterectomy more common in multiple gestations? *Obstet Gynecol* 2005; 105:1369–72.
- Forna F, Miles AM, Jamieson DJ. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy: a comparison of cesarean and postpartum hysterectomy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2004; 190:1440–4.
- Kacmar J, Bhimani L, Boyd M, Shah-Hosseini R, Peipert J. Route of delivery as a risk factor for emergent peripartum hysterectomy: a case-control study. *Obstet Gynecol* 2003;102: 141–45.
- Stanco LM, Schrimmer DB, Paul RH, Mishell DR Jr. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy and associated risk factors. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1993; 168:879–83.
- Kwee A, Bots ML, Visser GH, Bruinse HW. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy: A prospective study in The Netherlands. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 2006; 124:187–92.
- Menacker F. Trends in cesarean rates for first births and repeat cesarean rates for lowrisk women: United States, 1990-2003. *Natl Vital Stat Rep* 2005; 54:1–8.
- Hoyert DL, Mathews TJ, Menacker F, Strobino DM, Guyer B. Annual summary of vital statistics: 2004. *Pediatrics* 2006;117: 168–83
- Cengiz H, Yaşar L, Ekin M, Kaya C, Karakaş S. Management of intractable postpartum hemorrhage in a tertiary centre- A 5 year experience. *Niger Med J*. 2012;53(2):85-8.
- World Health Organization. Evaluating the Quality of Care for Severe Pregnancy Complications, the WHO Near-Miss Approach for Maternal Health. World Health Organization; 2011
- Anuradha C, Vani JY, Aruna V. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy-one year study in labour ward Obstetrics and Gynaec department Guntur Medical College, Guntur. (2014). *IOSR Journal of Nursing and Health Science (IOSR-JNHS)*. 2014;4(2)Ver. II:26-8.
- Pandher K, Sehgal DA, Aggarwal N. Frequency, indications and maternal outcome in obstetric hysterectomy in a tertiary care centre in India." *JK Science*. 2015;17(1):8-12.
- Abha S, Shrivastava C. Uterine Rupture: Still a Harsh Reality. *The*

- Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology of India. 2015;65(3):158-161
17. Umezurike CC, Feyi Waboso PA, Adisa CA. Peripartum hysterectomy in Aba Southeastern Nigeria. Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol 2008; 48:580-2.
 18. Zeteroglu S, Ustun Y, Engin Ustun Y, Sahin G, Kamaci M. Peripartum hysterectomy in a teaching hospital in the Eastern region of Turkey. Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol 2005; 120:57-62.
 19. Saxena SV, Bagga R, Jain V, Gopalan S. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy. Int J Gynaecol Obstet 2004; 85:172-3.